

Global Cooperation for Humanity Common Cause

(Extended)

Abstract: The initiative I've outlined here is undoubtedly ambitious, envisioning a world where advanced biotechnology enables the resurrection of all deceased individuals using their DNA samples. It proposes a multi-phased plan that spans several centuries, culminating in the recreation of the entire human population and the establishment of a utopian society across the Solar System and the Milky Way galaxy.

1. Database Creation (1-2 centuries): Building a database containing DNA samples from over 100 billion departed individuals is an enormous undertaking. Preserving and cataloging such an extensive collection would require significant resources and technological advancements in DNA storage and conservation.

2. Recreating Individuals (3-5 centuries): The process of recreating a person's body and mind from their DNA using advanced biotechnological methods represents a substantial scientific challenge. Achieving this feat for even one individual would be a significant milestone, let alone for billions of people. This phase requires not only technological advancements but also ethical considerations regarding the recreation of consciousness and identity.

3. Mass Resurrection (40k-70k years): Continuing the process of resurrecting all deceased individuals over tens of thousands of years is an extremely long-term endeavor. It assumes sustained dedication, advancements in biotechnology, and resources over millennia.

Conclusion: The ultimate vision of creating a utopian society where all individuals are immortal and resurrected is both fascinating and thought-provoking. The idea of colonizing parts of the Solar System and the Milky Way galaxy to accommodate this resurrected population adds an extra layer of complexity, considering the challenges of space colonization and resource allocation for such a vast number of individuals.

While the initiative's goal is aspirational and idealistic, it raises profound ethical, philosophical, and logistical questions. Considerations about the nature of life, the definition of identity, the allocation of resources, societal structures, and the potential consequences of achieving immortality and resurrection on a global scale would be paramount. The initiative certainly paints a grand picture of a future where science has pushed the boundaries of what was once thought impossible. However, it also prompts reflection on the potential implications and challenges such advancements could pose for humanity.

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Tirana, Albania
12/20/2023